

THREE-DIMENSIONAL CONTINUUM THEORY OF FAILURE PROPAGATION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN COMPRESSION

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Mechanism of beginning and propagation of failure in composite materials under three-axial, two-axial and uniaxial compression is considered. The beginning of failure is determined as a result of stability loss in material structure (internal instability). The analysis of internal instability is made within the framework of three-dimensional linearized theory of deformable bodies stability. The values of failure loads and regularities of failure propagation are determined from the condition of transition of main system of equations to the system of hyperbolic type. In continuum approximation composite materials are modelled by orthotropic elastic or elastic-plastic bodies with averaged constants.

The first time continuum three-dimensional theory of failure of composites in case of uniaxial compression was proposed by Guz' (Dokl.AN UkrSSR, 1969, No.3, pp.236-238, in Russian; more in detail in a monograph "Stability of three-dimensional deformable bodies", 1971, Kiev, 272 pp, in Russian). Basic statement of the continual theory are reduced to a following:

1. In continuum approximation laminated and fibrous composites with metal and polymer matrix are modelled by a compressible orthotropic body with the averaged constants. Since compressibility may develop in filler or matrix, an account must be taken of compressibility. In a case of elasto-plastic models the averaged constants are calculated at moment of stability loss.
2. Fracture or failure in compression occurs as a result of stability loss in a structure of a composite material (internal instability), quantities of breaking loads (theoretical strength limits) are determined from the condition of transition of the main linearized system of equations into a system of a hyperbolic type. It must be noted that corresponding linear system of equations for compressible solid is an elliptical system. In view of it, the surface of theoretical strength limits separates the region of hyperbolicity in the space of loading parameters.
3. Investigation of internal instability is carried out within the framework of three-dimensional linearized theory of deformable bodies stability including theory of finite precritical strains and two variants of theory of small precritical strains - according to Guz' (Foundations of three-dimensional theory of deformable body stability, 1986, Kiev, 512 pp, in Russian).
4. In an investigation of elastic-plastic materials (for composites with a metal matrix) within the framework of the three-dimensional linearised theory of deformable bodies stability the general conception of continuing loading is used in accordance with above mentioned monographs. In this connection the change of off-loading zones in the process of stability loss is not considered. The mentioned statement furnishes an opportunity to consider fracture or failure theory with utilization of elastic and plastic models uniformly.
5. It is assumed that loading is carried out by "dead" loads. In this connection, for investigation of stability the static method of three-dimensional theory of deformable bodies stability is used, since it was strictly proved in mentioned monographs. That in this case, for nonlinearly elastic and plastic models sufficient conditions of applicability of the static method are satisfied.
6. Since furthermore investigation is carried out for a point of a material (for a small vicinity of a point - for a small volume element of a continuum), the precritical state may vary in transition to the neighbouring point, thus the precritical state should be considered as a local-homogeneous.
7. As applied to the point under consideration, of a material, we will investigate the process of loading by compression of an uniformly distributed load (taking into account the statement 6) along axes of symmetry of the material only. In this case, before the process of fracture the homogeneous stress occurs in the form

$$(1) \quad S_{ij}^0 = d_{ij} S_{jj}^0; \quad S_{jj}^0 = const; \quad S_{ij}^0 < 0.$$

All values related to precritical state and corresponding loads before fracture or failure are de-noted by "0". It must be noted that the precritical state (the term accepted in the stability theory) may be called as the initial state corresponding to beginning of fracture or failure processes in fracture mechanics under consideration. At the beginning of fracture process in addition to the initial stress state in the form of Eqn 1 perturbances of the stress state appear, which, apparently, in value, may be considered less than stresses of the initial (precritical) state. The mentioned consideration, in a certain sense, substantiates the opportunity of application of the linearized theory for description of perturbances behavior at the beginning of fracture or failure processes. The utility of application of three-dimensional linearized theory is seemed to be evident, for it is difficult to propose sufficiently by one of applied two-dimensional theories for description of a relatively delicate phenomenon stability loss in structure of composite material.

In accordance with monographs of Guz', the system of differential equations in partial derivatives for compressible body has following form

$$W_{imab} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_b} u_a = 0; \quad i, m, a, b = 1; 2; 3; \quad (2)$$

where u_a are the perturbances of a displacements; W is the tensor of averaged constants, which are shown for various models in above mentioned monographs. In the case of three-axial compression there are following conditions

$$W_{imab} = W_{imab} (S_{11}^0, S_{22}^0, S_{33}^0), \quad S_{11}^0, S_{22}^0, S_{33}^0 = const. \quad (3)$$

It must be noted that we consider internal fracture in a composite material, which is determined by stability loss in structure of a composite material, i.e., by stability loss in microvolume. In the mechanism of fracture under consideration, changes must one way or another develop in macrovolume, and in the last case, therewith, they should not be considered (macrofracture).

The mentioned changes in microvolume must be reflected in properties, which do not depend on boundary conditions, since process of material fracture is being investigated (internal fracture corresponds to an "infinite" material) instead of influence of grips of testing machines, the form of transverse section etc. It is also apparent that changes in microvolume are determined by perturbances of displacements, which are described by the system Eqn 2. Thus, we may consider that beginning of fracture corresponds to an appearing of solutions of the system Eqn 2 with the notation Eqn 3, which do not depend on boundary conditions and do not have a local character. Given conditions for solution of the system Eqn 2 may be satisfied only in case, if the mentioned solutions contain solutions of a hyperbolic type, i.e., when the system Eqn 2 becomes the system of hyperbolic type. As is was mentioned, in case the absence of initial stresses Eqn 1 corresponding to a linear system of equations, which provides the uniqueness of solving of linear problems. Main approach is: the beginning of fracture or failure process may be identified with that moment in history of loading, when the system of differential equations Eqn 2 from elliptical system transforms to hyperbolic one, i.e., when the system Eqn 2 losses the property of ellipticity; theoretical strength limits, therewith, are also determined from this condition.

Within the framework of the continual theory of fracture or failure it is possible not only to determine quantities of theoretical strength limits in compression, failure of composite materials in compression, under consideration but to describe the nature of fracture or failure of composite materials in compression as well.

Since, perturbances in hyperbolic system propagate over characteristic planes and surfaces, we come to conclusion that fracture or failure occurs along characteristic planes and surfaces.

In case of uniaxial compression the theoretical results (on a base of above elucidated theory) is strictly proved that the failure propagates almost perpendicular to direction of compression.

Experimental results corresponds to above mentioned main theoretical results for case of uniaxial compression. The comparison with results of experiments with the specimens of a glass-cloth-base laminate, a glass-plastic (square cross-section, circular cross-section) and a boron-aluminum were realized.

